

1 Article

2 Risk Evaluation Decision-aiding Approach (RED-M)

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9 **Abstract:** Research indicates that different contexts require different risk evaluation approaches.
10 There is limited research on the most feasible risk evaluation approach for a specific complex social-
11 technical context. Also, there is limited guidance on how to develop a methodology to identify the
12 best risk evaluation approach for a specific social-technical context. We develop the risk evaluation
13 decision-aiding methodology that helps identify the best risk evaluation approach for Solotvyno.
14 Solotvyno is a small village situated on the border of Ukraine that faces the risk of land subsidence
15 due to the flooding of the salt domes. In order to identify the most suitable approach, we reviewed
16 multiple existing approaches. After an intensive literature review, we arrived at four possible risk
17 evaluation approaches, namely: German Advisory Council on Global Change (WBGU), the Th.
18 Plattner approach, The predictive, Bayesian risk classification scheme (PBRC Scheme) and the
19 Pollard approach. We made comparisons between the different approaches. After analysing each
20 approach, we concluded that the two approaches: WBGU and PBRC, are the most suitable in the
21 case of Solotvyno. Future research will entail applying one of the recommended approaches in
22 Solotvyno municipality and assessing the feasibility of the decision-aiding methodology to select a
23 viable risk evaluation approach.

24 **Keywords:** Risk Evaluation Approach; Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR); Risk Governance; Complex
25 Socio-technical System; Decision-aiding Methodology; Land Subsidence; Solotvyno municipality;
26 Community-based risk assessment; Tolerability and Acceptability Judgment; Risk Evaluation
27 Criteria.
28

29 1. Introduction

30 There are many different definitions of risk by researchers from diverse disciplines. By some, it
31 is the likelihood of occurrence of an event [1], for others, it is the consequences of an event [1, 2] while
32 others combine the two elements [3]. Other researchers define risk as uncertainty about the
33 occurrence of an event and the damage that might be incurred [4]. Various researchers propose one
34 common definition that entails both the likelihood of occurrence of an event and its possible
35 consequences [1, 4]. By combining these descriptions, we define risk as the likelihood of an event
36 occurring and the severity of its consequences. To clarify this definition, we provide two examples,
37 as follows:

- 38 1. The likelihood of dying because of a plane crash is so low that it is almost pointless to quantify.
39 However, the consequences in terms of loss of life, economic losses coupled with the
40 environmental impacts, are extremely large; hence, it is still perceived as a risk.
- 41 2. The likelihood of a child falling during their first bicycle ride is high; however, the consequence
42 is may not be severe. In this case, it is also perceived as a risk because the likelihood is high.

43 A person may decide to accept the risk of dying in a plane, or a child may decide to accept the
44 risk of falling during their first bicycle ride. These decisions are known as risk-taking decisions. Risk
45 evaluation is known as the process of deciding whether to accept, tolerate or avoid a risk. In this

46 paper, we define risk evaluation as making judgments regarding the tolerability and acceptability of
 47 a particular risk, depending on whether risk reduction measures are needed.

48 Risk evaluation is the third phase in risk governance [3]. The four phases of risk governance are
 49 pre-assessment, risk-appraisal, risk evaluation and risk management. Figure 1 visualizes this process.
 50 The main goal of risk evaluation is to determine the tolerability and the acceptability of a given risk,
 51 based on the scientific evidence collected in the risk appraisal phase and societal values [3, 5-7].
 52 Tolerability refers to a willingness to live with a particular risk as long as taking the risk is worth it
 53 and the risk is adequately controlled [8]. Acceptability only occurs when there is no need to take risk
 54 reduction measures to ensure safety [9]. Risk reduction measures only apply to tolerable risks.
 55 Acceptable risks do not require risk reduction measures. In the case of intolerable risks, the risk
 56 reduction measures outweigh the benefits of tolerating the specific risk.
 57

58

59 Figure 1. IRGC Risk Governance Framework. Source: Risk Governance Towards an Integrative
 60 Approach (Source: Ortwin Renn, 2005).

61 Risk evaluation takes place after risk appraisal and before risk management. Risk appraisal
 62 contains two sub-phases: risk assessment and concern assessment. At the risk assessment sub-
 63 phase the identification, describing, mapping and analysing of each hazard takes place according to
 64 its likelihood of occurrence and its consequences should a disaster occur. Afterwards, we assessed
 65 exposure and vulnerability and estimated whether the risk is high, moderate or low [6]. Analysing
 66 vulnerability takes place during the concern assessment sub-phase and entails risk perceptions, social
 67 concerns and socio-economic impacts. Thus, the risk appraisal phase gathers evidence on the hazard
 68 (risk assessment), exposure (risk assessment) and vulnerability (concern assessment).

69 Risk evaluation is a sub-phase of the tolerability and acceptability judgement phase and occurs
 70 before risk characterisation. In categorisation the creating of risk profiles take place, judgments on
 71 the seriousness of risk are made, and risk reduction options are taken into consideration. After the
 72 judgement of tolerability and acceptability, risk management takes place. Tolerability and
 73 acceptability judgments are critical in deciding whether there is a need for risk reduction measures.

74 Research indicates that individual risk-taking decisions are dependent on the nature of the risk
 75 and the societal context [10-14]. A person may choose to avoid, accept, transfer, mitigate or exploit a
 76 risk, based on the likelihood and consequences of the risk and their social context [12]. Kaspersen
 77 [10] explain that the context a person is in affects their decision and preferences. Müller and Rau [12],
 78 conclude that the social context, the societal preferences and the level of heterogeneity of a particular
 79 risk affects the individual decision whether or not to take the risk. This research demonstrates that

80 “people’s choices are not only context-dependent but are sensitive to their degree of inequality
81 aversion” [12], (p. 116). Li and Yu [11] explain context-dependent choice using the foraging theory to
82 explain the persistence of choice behaviour and provide insights regarding “unchosen alternatives”
83 [11], (p. 170). Therefore, choosing a specific risk evaluation approach for a particular social context
84 may be better than using the same approach in any context.

85 Furthermore, in some social contexts determining the likelihood and consequences of a
86 particular risk is highly uncertain. These social contexts are known as complex socio-technical
87 systems. Onencan [15], (p. 1) explains that “socio-technical systems emphasise social (actors,
88 networks, organisations) and technical systems, in the design, analysis and systems operation.”
89 According to Sheard [16] complex systems

90 “do not have a centralising authority and are not designed from a known specification, but
91 instead involve disparate stakeholders creating systems that are functional for other purposes
92 and are only brought together in the complex system because the individual “agents” of the
93 system see such cooperation as being beneficial for them.”

94 Solotvyno municipality, which is the selected case study in this paper, qualifies as a complex
95 socio-technical context because of the following qualities:

96 We selected Solotvyno because of her specific socio-technical situation. It is a small village
97 situated in the Tyachev district of the Transcarpathian region of Ukraine that faces the risk of land
98 subsidence due to the flooding of the salt domes. It is located close to the border with Romania, on
99 the right bank of the Tisza River. The Carpathian sea deposited kilometres of high-quality salt many
100 mega-annums ago [17]. Since the 1790s, salt has been mined in this area [18]. This process remained
101 uninterrupted because there was clay protecting the upper part of the salt-dome [19]. To enable salt
102 mining in the upper part of the salt-dome, the mining company removed the protective layer. In 1908
103 water began to filtrate the galleries, thereby dissolving the salt leading to flooding in the salt-mines
104 [17]. This led to the formation of Lake Cunegunda [18]. The mines flooded and the water slowly
105 moved into the cavities, dissolving the salt and the land slowly subsided. As a result of the eroded
106 rock salt domes the ground subsided, and in some parts collapsed, leading to deformation of several
107 houses [18]. Looking at those consequences, it becomes clear that the salt mining has created certain
108 risks. Because of this risk, risk evaluation is needed to judge the acceptability and tolerability.

109 One key challenge facing disaster risk reduction (DRR) is decision science neither provides
110 guidance nor a universally accepted methodology to select a suitable risk evaluation approach, for a
111 particular complex socio-technical system [20]. While we know that different social-technical contexts
112 need different risk evaluation approaches, it is difficult for DRR experts to choose between various
113 existing methods. Also, though various risk evaluation approaches exist, very few have been tried
114 and tested in various complex socio-technical contexts.

115 The absence of a single, empirically verified and universally accepted methodology for selecting
116 the appropriate risk evaluation approach for a select complex socio-technical context, is a significant
117 challenge. The existing risk evaluation approaches have fundamental differences in terms

118 The main goal of this paper is to design a methodology for selecting the most suitable evaluation
119 approach for a given complex socio-technical context. The selected complex socio-technical context
120 is situated risk governance of Solotvyno municipality.

121 The main question that we seek to answer in this paper is: “How do you develop a methodology
122 to identify the best risk evaluation approach for a specific social-technical context?”. To answer the
123 research question, we developed a methodology to identify the best risk evaluation approach for
124 Solotvyno. Due to the different existing approaches, there must also be a method that guides DRR-
125 experts in choosing one. The purpose of this paper is to design this method.

126 In order to find a suitable risk evaluation approach for Solotvyno, we analysed multiple existing
127 approaches and selected four possible risk evaluation approaches that matched our definition. These
128 four approaches are the approach by the German Advisory Council on Global Change (WBGU), the
129 Th. Plattner approach, The predictive, Bayesian risk classification scheme(PBRC scheme) approach
130 and the Pollard approach [5, 21-23]. The four approaches were compared based on various criteria,
131 and two approaches: WBGU and the PBRC Scheme were found to be most suitable for Solotvyno

132 municipality. The results are useful for direct application, in the case of Solotvyno, regarding the
133 subsidence risk. However, the methodology can also be used by researchers to identify the most
134 feasible risk evaluation approach for a particular socio-technical context.

135 This paper is structured as follows. Section two presents the analytical framework. After that,
136 the method of the literature review and the literature review process. Section 4 contains the results,
137 including the strengths and weaknesses of the different approaches. Section 5 discusses which
138 approach is considered most suitable for Solotvyno.

139 2. Towards a Risk Evaluation Decision-aiding Criteria

140 The goal of risk evaluation is to determine the tolerability and the acceptability of a given risk [5]. To
141 determine which approach is most applicable to the Solotvyno case, the different approaches must
142 be assessed to decide whether they aid in reaching the primary goal for the evaluation for that
143 particular context. Most DRR experts use a criterion to determine the tolerability and acceptability of
144 a risk [24-26]. Those criteria are useful for defining the exact format of the parameters used for
145 decision making [27]. Use of criteria is preferred by DRR experts who seek clarity and structure to
146 present the results and their analysis. For this paper, we selected to use the risk acceptance criteria to
147 present the results, including the comparisons between the different approaches.
148

149 2.1. Existing Risk Evaluation Criterion

150 To be able to assess the approaches with the use of risk acceptance criteria, firstly the existing risk
151 acceptance criteria will be explained. Various researchers came up with risk evaluation criteria that,
152 according to their research, should be included in an approach in order to correctly evaluate risk. In
153 the following paragraphs, the risk evaluation criteria of 3 researchers will be explained.

154 2.1.1 The Health and Safety Executive criterion (HSE criterion)

155 The HSE is an organisation with the mission to prevent work-related death, injury and ill health.
156 HSE's roots stretch back to 1833 and with expertise in risk assessment. The Health and Safety
157 Executive (HSE) [28] propose three criteria for determining the tolerability and the acceptability of a
158 given risk: the equity-based criterion, the utility-based criterion, and the technology-based criterion.

159 The equity-based criterion starts the premise that all individuals have a right to minimal
160 protection. The criterion can be implemented by establishing a maximum limit above which no
161 individual can be exposed in order to ensure minimal individual safety.

162 The utility-based criterion regards to the trade-off between the costs and benefits of taking
163 measures to reduce risk. It is the process of determining if the benefits resulting from the measures
164 are worth the required investment. According to French et al. (2005, Ref. 15), the costs linked to a risk
165 can be divided in three parts, i.e. (i) the costs linked to safety (implementation of risk reduction
166 measures); (ii) the costs linked to the impacts of the risk on the workers (professional diseases and
167 accidents); and (iii) the costs linked to the consequences of the risk to the public.

168 The technology-based criterion indicates if there is already a way to reach acceptable or tolerable
169 risk through the use of practices such as standards and professional practice. The danger of this
170 criterion is the fact that it can lead to ignoring the costs related to using those standards and practices.
171

172 2.1.2 Vrijling, Hengel and Houben criterion

173 J.K. Vrijling, W. van Hengel and R.J. Houben are three engineers from the faculty of civil
174 engineering, which is a faculty of the Technical University of Delft. Research done by J.K. Vrijling,
175 W. van Hengel and R.J. Houben [29] revealed that there are two points of views in studies of the
176 acceptability of risk. The first point of view is that an individual weighs risk against direct and
177 indirect personal benefits. In other words, the decision to accept risk has a cost/benefit character. This
178 point of view leads to the personally acceptable level of risk with this proposed definition by Vrijling

179 et al. [29] : “The frequency at which an individual may be expected to sustain a given level of harm
180 from the realisation of specified hazards.” The second point of view is the degree of voluntariness
181 with which the decision is taken, and the degree of risk endured. Although the societal decision-
182 making process weighs the social benefits against social costs, including risk, this process of appraisal
183 is not easily made explicit.

184 2.1.3 Kasperson criterion

185 Roger E. Kasperson is an American risk analyst, research Professor and a Distinguished Scientist.
186 In the research called acceptability of human risk, Roger E. Kasperson states that the following five
187 contexts or comparisons are paramount for judging risk acceptability: the risk as compared with
188 natural background, the risk compared with other risks prevalent in society, the risk in the context of
189 the magnitude of associated benefits, the costs of risk reduction, and the risks of available substitutes
190 [9]. The risk as compared with natural background suggests an increment to risk afforded by
191 performing a specific activity. The second comparison is the risk compared with other risks prevalent
192 in society. For example the comparison between risks previously determined to be tolerable by a
193 particular risk guardian. The third context that Kasperson mentions is the risk in the context of the
194 magnitude of associated benefits. Together with the fourth context of the costs of risk reduction, this
195 is seen as a trade-off between costs and benefits. The final analysis involves the examination of risks
196 of available substitutes. Actions designed to reduce risks sometimes create new and perhaps more
197 considerable risks.
198

199 2.2 The Risk Evaluation Decision-aiding Criteria

200 To arrive at a extensive set of criteria, we included all three of the studies above. After compiling all
201 the criterion from the three studies, we ended up with a total of 9 risk acceptance criteria. We have
202 merged the corresponding criteria to create a clear structure. Figure 2 shows which criterion are
203 merged.

Figure 1. Merging of the criteria

204
205
206
207
208
209
210

We identified nine elements combined into three criteria. The aim is not to find the approach that includes the most elements, but the approach that includes all the most critical elements for Solotvyno municipality. That is why it is crucial that we first explain how unique Solotvyno is and why it is necessary to look for a specific approach.

211 2.2 Uniqueness of Solotvyno and the Risk Evaluation Criteria

212 Every case has its own set of essential elements that should be included in the risk evaluation
213 approach [12]. Hence, the risk is created by various actors who sometimes benefit from this risk while
214 other people living in Solotvyno bear the risks. The fact that people benefiting are benefitting from
215 the risk makes the case more complex, and that is why it requires a particular approach. When an
216 actor concludes that it is more beneficial to take the risk, he accepts the risks and tries to manage it
217 instead of mitigating it [30].

218 The criteria of costs related to risk reduction is vital for Solotvyno as well. There was less
219 allocation of money to manage water in the mine when the Russian government was no longer

220 managing the mines [17]. Even more important are the costs of filling the created holes, reclaiming
221 the land and removing the objects that have remained of the mining shafts. Therefore, the costs
222 related to risk reduction do have a significant impact on the risk level in Solotvyno.

223 The risk in the context of the magnitude of associated benefits is also particularly relevant for
224 the Solotvyno case. is due to approximately the same reason as with the first element, namely the fact
225 that some people benefit from the cause of the risk.

226 The degree of voluntariness element also has to be considered because some inhabitants
227 accepted the risk by continuing to either live or conduct business in the high-risk zones. Even though
228 the inhabitants are free to move wherever they want, their options are limited if they cannot find a
229 job, a suitable school or place of worship, in the new place, so they choose to stay in Solotvyno. Mishra
230 et al. [31] created a place attachment scale, which consists of 18 items to assess the level that a person
231 is attached to a specific place [31]. This elements in the scale explain various reasons why the
232 Solotvyno inhabitants could choose to stay[31]. By the place attachment scale, literature review and
233 the interviews conducted in Solotvyno, the inhabitants of Solotvyno feel attached to the place, due
234 to:

- 235 1. The inhabitants are of mixed origin, and Solotvyno is the only place that they do not feel the
236 pressure to integrate. The municipality governance structure has taken account of the
237 complexity of its inhabitants and supported the emergence of nationality-based schools,
238 multiple religious places and
- 239 2. The main burial site is on a hill where most of the inhabitant's forefathers are buried, and they
240 need proximity to the place to visit their deceased loved ones regularly and later would like to
241 be buried next to their forefathers. Relocation would reduce the chances of being buried with
242 their family, and they cannot move with their deceased loved ones.
- 243 3. Its proximity to the Romanian-Ukrainian border, which provides a livelihood to some of them
244 through cross-border trade.
- 245 4. The inhabitants have friends and relatives living there who provide emotional and financial
246 support.
- 247 5. The inhabitant's own houses and businesses in that place and some are extremely big and
248 expensive.
- 249 6. There is a booming business every summer, at the recreational area, where the Salt Lakes are
250 located.
- 251 7. It is a small municipality and people know each other by name, which makes it home for the
252 inhabitants.

253
254 The place attachment indicators show that most of the current Solotvyno inhabitants prefer not
255 to leave their current environment [32]. Because there may be cases where individuals and groups
256 accept the risk when serious risk reduction measures have to be taken, this risk is a problem.
257

258 3. Materials and Methods

259 In this method section, we have extensively described the steps we took to develop the
260 methodology, the choices we made and the rationale. This study used a systematic literature review
261 in order to investigate past research that developed a qualitative risk evaluation approach. It was
262 decided to focus on non-mathematical approaches so that the research did not become too extensive
263 and we were able to finish it in the given time. During a systematic literature review, it is imperative
264 to stay critical and focused because not all sources and articles are reliable [33].

265 We first looked up and compared different definitions of risk. Then we derived a set of keywords
266 that we chose to use as consistent search terms when searching all resources [33]. The search terms
267 we have used are: risk (A1), risk definition (A2), risk probability (A3), risk consequence (A4), define
268 risk (A5) and what is a risk (A6).

269 After defining risk, we needed to explain the risk governance framework, so we searched for
 270 risk articles that included a detailed explanation of this process. We decided to use one of the articles
 271 that we already found during our search for definitions of risk.

272 In order to compare different community-based risk evaluation approaches, we had to find the
 273 existing approaches. We used a third set of search terms to find articles on community-based risk
 274 evaluation approaches. This last set consists of the search terms: risk evaluation approaches (B1),
 275 community-based risk evaluation (B2), community-based risk evaluation approaches (B3), risk
 276 evaluation methods (B4) and criteria for evaluating risk (B5). To narrow down the publications, We
 277 have combined those terms with disaster, hazard or natural hazard.

278 In order to find studies about the risk, we have used five different electronic databases, namely:

- 279 1. Google Scholar
- 280 2. Scopus
- 281 3. ScienceDirect
- 282 4. SpringerLink
- 283 5. JSTOR.

284

285 We used those databases because all of them contain a lot of scientific papers that can be of great
 286 value to our research. **Error! Reference source not found.** summarises all the strategies used for
 287 finding evaluation approaches and the outcome.

288

289 **Table 1.** Search strategies for evaluation approaches.

Keywords	Databases	Search outcome	Last date of search
	Google Scholar	1010	01/05/2019
	ScienceDirect	190	
("risk evaluation approaches" OR "community-based risk evaluation" OR "community-based risk evaluation approaches" OR "risk evaluation methods" OR "criteria for evaluating risk") AND ("disaster" OR "natural hazards" OR "hazards")	SpringerLink	177	
	Scopus	74	
	JSTOR	5	

290

291 In total, we obtained 1456 publications from searching for electronic databases. To filter the right
 292 articles from the first set of publications, a selection was made based on the title of the publications.
 293 We looked at whether the title was related to the research subject.

294 Establishing inclusion and exclusion criteria for study participants is a standard, required
 295 practice when designing high-quality research protocols [34]. Table 2 presents the inclusion and
 296 exclusion criteria used for this systematic review. There was no restriction applied to the date of
 297 studies sampled, and we searched all databases for studies published up to 01/05/2019.

298

Table 2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria	• Publications must be peer-reviewed
---------------------------	--------------------------------------

- Publications that describe risk evaluation and not risk analysis or risk identification
- Publications that describe a specific usable approach

Exclusion criteria

- Publications that describe a part of risk assessment that is too specific
- Publications that are not written in Dutch or in English
- Publications that are only available as abstract

299

300 To make sure the articles are valid and reliable, we restricted the search to peer-reviewed articles.
 301 Furthermore, because we are researching risk evaluation approaches, the approaches must be risk
 302 evaluation approaches and not risk assessment approaches. To assess whether an approach was for
 303 risk evaluation, we checked whether the approach considered the evidence only or evidence and
 304 values. We also eliminated the publications that were not Dutch or English and the articles that we
 305 could not access the full copy while scanning the titles. Abstract only articles were excluded because
 306 we needed a detailed explanation of the different approaches.

307 After this step, the number of relevant publications reduced from 1456 to 40. We then read the
 308 abstract of all 40 articles, and on that basis, we selected the relevant articles. After reading all the
 309 abstracts and eliminating unsuitable publications based on the exclusion criteria, we arrived at only
 310 12 articles. Because 12 articles are relatively few, we decided to use the snowballing method.

311 We started with backward snowballing, which means identifying relevant publications from the
 312 reference list of the most relevant publication that passed the quality assessment step. When we
 313 finished backward snowballing, we applied forward snowballing [35]. Forward snowballing implies
 314 checking the publications that cite publications that are considered relevant and passed the
 315 assessment step. All the papers that we found through snowballing underwent the same assessment
 316 step, as mentioned earlier in the section.

317 After the snowballing, we had 23 articles found via the search terms and four articles extra that
 318 we came across during the research. Those remaining articles' full texts were read to arrive at the
 319 final selection. Figure 2 is a visualisation of the selection process.

320

321

Figure 2. Article selection flow chart

Some of the publications we found included a risk evaluation approach. Because the research aims to identify which approach suits the Sotolvyno case, we also searched for requirements for an effective risk evaluation approach. Therefore, we searched for publications that included criteria that could be used for determining the tolerability and the acceptability of risk. Using the search term “risk acceptance criteria,” we found three relevant and peer-reviewed articles.

In sub-section 2.2, we selected nine sub-criteria to use for determining the tolerability and the acceptability of risk comprising of 3 main criteria.

After that, we analyzed whether each of the nine elements in the Risk Evaluation Decision-aiding Methodology Those elements are placed in the rows of table 3, and the approaches are the columns. When we concluded that an approach takes an element into account, we placed a checkmark in the row of that element.

4. Results

4.1 Risk evaluation approaches

In this section we explain the found approaches in detail. All criteria will be checked and explained to enable a good comparison of the approaches.

Table 3. Risk evaluation approaches

Approach	Main factors	Reference
WBGU	Nine criteria: Extent of damage, Probability of occurrence, Extent of damage, Incertitude, Ubiquity, Persistency, Reversibility, Delay effect, Violation of equity, Potential of mobilisation	Klinke and Renn [5]
Th. Plattner approach	Six criteria: Voluntariness, Reducibility, Knowledge, Endangerment, Extent of damage, Frequency of event	Plattner [23]
PBRC Scheme	Nine characteristics: Potential consequences, Uncertainty about consequences, Ubiquity, Persistency, Delay effect, Reversibility, Violation of equity, Potential of mobilisation and the difficulty in establishing appropriate performance measures.	Kristensen, Aven [21]
Pollard approach	Seventeen criteria: Stock at Risk, Knock-on Effects, Spatial Extent, Heterogeneity, Spatial Extent, Sensitivity of Receptor, Severity of Effect, Temporal Extent, Latency, Accumulation, Reversibility, Scarcity, Notoriety, Unfairness, Imposition, Distrust.	Pollard, Davidson [22]

Table 3 shows the risk evaluation approaches that we encountered during the literature review. All the approaches make use of a variety of criterion to evaluate a given risk. These approaches can be considered as risk evaluation approaches because they do contain de societal aspects as well as the technical aspects of risk. To find out which approach is most applicable to the Sotolvyno case, we must analyze the approaches on their strengths and weaknesses, and then the best fit for the Sotolvyno must be determined.

348 4.2 Selected Risk Evaluation Approaches

349 First, we will briefly explain the approaches that were found during the literature review to gain
 350 a better understanding of all the approaches and their purposes. For each approach, the risk
 351 evaluation criterion will be explained.
 352

353 4.2.1 WBGU approach

354 Klinke and Renn decided that they wanted to include more criteria than the classic components
 355 such as the extent of damage and the probability of occurrence. To find more criteria they looked into
 356 the researches of Boholm in 1998, Sjöberg in 1999, Slovic in 1987 and 1992 and Rohrman & Renn in
 357 2000. The result was a long list of criteria that was not identical for different groups. The WBGU had
 358 addressed this problem by involving many experts in finding the most suitable criteria. These criteria
 359 ended up to be: the extent of damage, probability of occurrence, the extent of damage, uncertainty,
 360 ubiquity, persistency, reversibility, delay effect, violation of equity and potential of mobilisation.

361 The extent of damage is about the adverse effects in, for example, the number of deaths or the
 362 number of injured. The probability of occurrence is an estimate for the relative frequency of a discrete
 363 or continuous loss function. Uncertainty is the umbrella term for all uncertain components. Ubiquity
 364 indicates the degree of the geographical spread of potential damages and persistency indicates the
 365 degree of temporal spread of potential damages. By reversibility we mean the possibility to restore
 366 the situation to the state before the damage occurred. The delay effect describes the delay between
 367 the activity and the actual impact of that activity. Violation of equity is about the discrepancy between
 368 those who enjoy the benefits and those who bear the risks.

369 **Klinke and Renn decided to divide the potential of mobilisation criteria into four major elements:**

- 370 1. **Inequity and injustice associated with the distribution of risks and benefits over time, space, and**
 371 **social status (thus covering the criterion of equity).**
- 372 2. **Psychological stress and discomfort associated with the risk or the risk source (as measured by**
 373 **psychometric scales).**
- 374 3. **Potential for social conflict and mobilisation (degree of political or public pressure on risk**
 375 **regulatory agencies).**
- 376 4. **Spill-over effects that are likely to be expected when highly symbolic losses have repercussions**
 377 **on other fields such as financial markets or loss of credibility in management institutions.**
 378

379 4.2.2 Th. Plattner approach

380 In his research, Plattner suggests that evaluation criteria can be used to compute the perceived
 381 individual risk and acceptable individual risk. The factors he found focuses on natural hazard risk
 382 perception on the individual level. We compiled the list of factors The list of factors based on the
 383 literature on risk perception. The factors found were then presented to a group of experts who
 384 selected the most relevant factors. The factors found are as follows: voluntariness, reducibility,
 385 knowledge, endangerment, the extent of damage and frequency of the event. Some of those factors
 386 have a slightly more extensive meaning; Table 5 shows what each factor represents.
 387

388 **Table 4.** Th. Plattner evaluation criteria

Evaluation criteria	Represents
Voluntariness:	Voluntariness
Reducibility:	Reducibility, Predictability, Avoidability

Knowledge:	Familiarity, Knowledge about risk, Manageability
Endangerment:	Controllability, Number of people affected, Fatality of consequences, Distribution of victims, Scope of area affected, Immediacy of effects, Directness of impact
Extent of damage:	Extent of damage
Frequency of event:	Frequency of event

389

390 *4.2.3 PBRC Scheme*

391 Kristensen and Aven criticised the WBGU approach of Klinke and Renn. Their main point of
392 critique was related to the understanding and meaning of what risk is. Kristensen and Aven present
393 a Bayesian risk classification schema based on the WBGU schema, which they believe therefore is
394 considered as a modified version of the WBGU schema. The PBRC schema consists of nine
395 characteristics. Some of the characteristics are taken directly from the WBGU schema, some are
396 modified, and some are new. The nine proposed characteristics are potential consequences,
397 uncertainty about consequences, ubiquity, persistency, delay effect, reversibility, violation of equity,
398 the potential of mobilisation and the difficulty in establishing appropriate performance measures.
399 We will only discuss the modified and new characteristics in detail, for the other character see section
400 3.2.1. The two characteristics: potential consequences and uncertainty about consequences are the
401 two key characteristics, while the other seven characteristics are used to describe aspects of these two
402 characteristics. The potential consequence is indicated with observable quantities like the number of
403 fatalities or the number of injuries. Factors such as variability in humans, animals, plants and
404 technical systems; systematic and random measurement errors within the data used as background
405 information; indeterminacy resulting from a genuine stochastic relationship between cause and
406 effects etc. should all be taken into consideration when assessing the uncertainty about consequences.
407 A new characteristic that Kristensen and Aven included is the difficulty in establishing appropriate
408 performance measures. This characteristic is included in order to represent this aspect of risk
409 assessment. They recommend qualitatively describing this characteristic so the experts can give their
410 opinion about the appropriateness of the selected quantities or measures on a scale from, for example, 0
411 to 10.
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413 *4.2.4 Pollard approach*

414 The Pollard approach consists of 17 attributes that are classified according to those characterising the
415 physical properties of the harm and those characterising the social response or valuation of the harm.
416 We will briefly explain each of those attributes:
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Table 5. Explanations of the Pollard attributes

Attribute	Explanation
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Stock at Risk	Represents a valuation of the overall harm, either in economic terms or in terms of numbers of receptors.
Knock-on Effects	Reflects that harm to one receptor may affect the wellbeing of another receptor.
Spatial Extent	Denotes the overall area in which exposures to the hazard that causes environmental harm are experienced.
Heterogeneity	Reflects that within the overall area denoted by Spatial Extent, there may be heterogeneity in exposure to the hazard.
Sensitivity of Receptor	Reflects the proportion of receptors exposed that exhibit the harm.
Severity of Effect	Defines the general physical effect on an individual sensitive receptor only.
Temporal Extent	Denotes the length of time that the environmental harm will be experienced.
Latency	The period of time before the consequent environmental harm starts to be realized during the hazard.
Accumulation	The changes in rate at which the harm progresses over time.
Reversibility	Considers both whether the effects of the harm are reversible and, if so, over what time scale.
Scarcity	Reflects the abundance of the receptor, and is used to consider the loss of cultural resources, as well as physical environments.
Dread	Reflects that society can have an aversion to, or fear of, a harm that may be largely unrelated to its physical nature.
Unfamiliarity	Gives an assessment of concern that may arise out of a low degree of knowledge and understanding of the harm.
Notoriety	Reflects the potential for raised awareness of, and anxiety about, the harm via the media and other channels and information.
Unfairness	Reflects the discontent that may arise from the inequity or unfairness of a harm's distribution.
Imposition	

	Measures the social value afforded by the degree of personal control over the harm.
Distrust	Captures the consequences of a lack of trust in the characterisation of the harm or in those responsible for its management.

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In order to see which approach scores on which criteria, we formulated an element for each of the criterion mentioned above. We ended up with the following set of elements: Does the approach include/take into account?

1. the cost/benefit character? (U1)
2. the costs related to risk reduction? (U2)
3. the magnitude of associated benefits? (U3)
4. a criterion specifically focused on not passing a maximum? (E1)
5. a criterion that compares the risk with other risks prevalent in society? (E2)
6. a criterion that takes the degree of voluntariness to account? (E3)
7. a criterion that compares the risk with the risk level during the natural background? (T1)
8. a criterion that focuses on existing solutions? (T2)
9. a criterion that also looks at the risks of available substitutes? (T3)

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Table 6. Results of Applying the Risk Evaluation Methodology

Approaches		WBGU	Th. Plattner approach	PBRC Scheme	Pollard approach
Utility-based criterion	U1	✓		✓	✓
	U2	✓	✓	✓	✓
	U3	✓		✓	
Equity-based criterion	E1	✓		✓	
	E2		✓		✓
	E3	✓	✓	✓	✓
Technology-based criterion	T1		✓	✓	
	T2	✓	✓	✓	
	T3				

434

Table 6 gives a structured and organised way of which elements each approach includes. The WBGU approach and the PBRC Schema contain the most elements. The Th. Plattner approach focuses more on the equity-based criterion and the technology-based criterion and does not cover the utility-based criterion. The Pollard approach does not contain any element of the technology-based criterion but scores good on the utility-based criterion and the equity-based criterion.

440

In section 2.2, we explained the uniqueness of Solotvyno by the importance of a few of the elements. These were the following elements: The cost/benefit character, The costs of risk reduction, The risk in the context of the magnitude of associated benefits, Degree of voluntariness and Existing solutions. In order to pick the best approach for the Solotvyno case, we must look at which approach contains most of these elements.

446

Table 8.

Approaches	WBGU	Th. Plattner approach	PBRC Scheme	Pollard approach
The cost/benefit character	✓		✓	✓

The cost of risk reduction	✓	✓	✓	✓
The risk in the context of the magnitude of associated benefits	✓		✓	
Degree of voluntariness	✓	✓	✓	✓
Existing solutions	✓	✓	✓	

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Table 8 shows that two approaches meet all the requirement of a sound risk evaluation approach for Solutvyno. These are the WBGU approach and the PBRC scheme approach. Because the PBRC Scheme contains one extra element that is considered essential for effective risk evaluation, we conclude that the PBRC Schema is the most suitable approach for Solutvyno.

During our research, we encountered a few striking findings. We will explain all the findings, the assumptions and limitations and the suggested future research in the discussion section.

456

5. Discussion

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The findings are discussed based on the three main criteria; utility-based criterion, equity-based criterion and technology-based criterion. The implications of these findings will also be discussed in this section.

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5.1 WBGU

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The WBGU approach meets the first element of taking the cost/benefit character into accountability. We have concluded this because the article writes about the inequity and injustice associated with the distribution of risks and benefits over time, space, and social status [5].

The approach takes the second element about the cost related to risk reduction into accountability. Because reversibility is taken into consideration, automatically the costs of possible resources are considered.

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The approach considers the magnitude of associated benefits; this appears from the description of the violation of equity. In the article, they state that violation of equity describes the discrepancy between those who enjoy the benefits and those who bear the risks [5]. The violation of equity criteria shows that the associated benefits are taking into accountability.

The approach includes a criterion specifically focused on not passing a maximum, namely potential of mobilisation. This criterion involves the violation of individual, social, or cultural interests and values.

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The approach also includes the criterion that takes the degree of voluntariness into account. This as a result of the violation of equity criteria. As mentioned above, this criterion describes the discrepancy between those who enjoy the benefits and those who bear the risks. The discrepancy shows that there are also ways to take advantage of the risk, which means that people can take the risk voluntarily.

The last element that the approach meets is the criterion that focuses on existing solutions, which can be assumed based on the reversibility criteria. Reversibility describes the possibility to restore the situation to the state before the damage occurred [5]. When looking for possibilities, existing solutions have to be taken into consideration.

483 5.2 Th. Plattner approach

484 The Th. Plattner approach meets the second element because of the manageability criterion.
485 Managing is about reducing and controlling risk and therefore takes the costs related to risk reduction
486 into accountability.

487 The next included element that is the criterion that compares the risk with other risks prevalent in
488 society as a result the familiarity criteria. Familiarity can be defined as close acquaintance with or
489 knowledge of something. Comparing the risk with other risks prevalent in society is a useful and
490 widely used method for gaining knowledge.

491 The approach also takes voluntariness into accountability. The inclusion of this element is relatively
492 clear due to the voluntariness criteria.

493 The approach meets the element of comparing the risk with the risk level during the natural
494 background as well. The criteria of knowledge about risk is associated with knowledge about the
495 difference in risk during different situations.

496 The last element that is included is the criterion that focuses on existing solutions. The combination
497 of three criterion avoidability, manageability and controllability make sure of that. In order to find
498 out is a risk is avoidable, manageable or controllable, first existing solutions will be looked at.

499 5.3 PBRC Scheme

500 The PBRC Schema is a modified version of the WBGU approach. In order to score this approach, we
501 first adopted all the ticks from the WBGU approach. Secondly, we analysed the new and modified
502 criterion and decided whether ticks should be removed or added. The new or modified criterion are:

- 503 1. Potential consequences—represented by observable quantities
- 504 2. Uncertainty about consequences—represented by probability distributions for observable
505 quantities
- 506 3. The difficulty in establishing appropriate (representative) performance measures

507
508 The first criterion causes an extra tick for the element that compares the risk with the risk level
509 during the natural background. The criterion focuses on the potential consequences, and is
510 complemented by a comparison of risk in different scenarios.

511 The second criteria of uncertainty about consequences did not influence the number of ticks of
512 the PBRC Scheme approach.

513 The third criteria about the difficulty in establishing appropriate performance measures also do
514 not change the number of ticks.

515 5.4 Pollard approach

516 The Pollard approach includes the first element of taking the cost/benefit character into account
517 due to the unfairness criteria which is described as: “reflects the discontent that may arise from the
518 inequity or unfairness of a harm's distribution.” This shows that not everyone is bearing the risk, but
519 some people are risk-free or benefit from the risk.

520 The element about costs related to risk reduction is being met due to the reversibility criteria.
521 Just as explained for the other approaches, when reversibility is taken into consideration, the costs of
522 possible resources are too.

523 A criterion that compares the risk with other risks prevalent in society is also considered. The
524 inclusion of this element is due to the unfamiliarity criteria, which can be explained as: assesses
525 concern that may arise out of a low degree of knowledge and understanding of the harm. If the risk
526 has already occurred before, there will be a better knowledge of the risk and better understanding of
527 the consequences.

528 The last element met, is the element of taking the degree of voluntariness into account. The
529 inclusion of this element appears from the imposition criteria which has: “measures the social value
530 afforded by the degree of personal control over the harm” as an explanation. The degree of personal
531 control is considered equal to the degree of voluntariness.

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533 5.5 RED-M explanation

534 Introduction

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538 First a literature review has to be performed. By defining a set of search terms that describe the
 539 wanted risk evaluation approaches, a systematic search for articles including risk evaluation
 540 approaches can be conducted. When the useful articles are selected based on the inclusion and
 541 exclusion criteria, the risk evaluation articles have to be separated from the risk assessment articles.

542 It must therefore be considered here whether the focus is on acceptability and tolerability and not on
 543 identification or estimation. With too few found articles, the snowballing method can be used. Then
 544 again, the risk evaluation articles have to be distinguished from the risk assessment articles. The last
 545 step of the literature review is picking the actual approaches from the articles and describing them in
 546 detail. An extensive explanation is needed for a good analyzation in the last step.

547 The next step is selecting the specific priority criteria for the chosen case study. In order to do so
 548 the risk assessment report and the concern assessment report have to be analyzed. After the
 549 analyzation the current situation has to be compared with the reports. The contradictions between
 550 the reality and the reports have to be identified and explained further with information found during
 551 a subsequent literature review. Place attachment also plays an important role in selecting priority
 552 criteria and therefore has to be reviewed. Finally the current situation has to be compared with the 9
 553 risk evaluation criteria to compile a list of priority criteria for the case study.

554 The aforementioned risk evaluation criteria are established by combining multiple risk
 555 evaluation criteria into groups. The more general risk evaluation criteria of HSE have been chosen as
 556 grouping criteria. Although the criteria from Vrijling et al. [29] and Kasperson [9] are only about risk
 557 acceptability, we considered them as useful because they were grouped into the HSE criteria and
 558 those do take tolerability into account. The criteria that are grouped under the utility-based criterion
 559 are all focused on either costs or benefits or both of them. Under the equity-based criterion we
 560 grouped the elements with the emphasis on the rights and feelings of individuals. The third criteria
 about technology includes elements regarding to existing solutions and any new related risks.

561 At last the found approaches have to be ranked based on how many priority criteria they
 562 include. All evaluation criteria must be checked for each approach. As guidance on how to decide
 563 whether an approach includes an element we composed a checklist. For this checklist, see figure 4.
 564

An approach includes **the cost/benefit character** when it incorporates:

- Costs (money, deaths or injured) and benefits (money or jobs).
- Violation of equity (people are enjoying benefits while others are bearing the risk).

An approach includes **the costs of risk reduction** when it incorporates:

- Costs related to proposed risk reduction measures.
- "How much society wishes to spend to avoid a particular consequence." ¹

An approach includes **the risk in the context of the magnitude of associated benefits** when it incorporates:

- A comparison of risk and benefits.
- A determination of how much risk reduction should be undertaken.

An approach includes **a maximal limit that cannot be crossed** when it incorporates:

- "The premise that all individuals have unconditional rights to certain levels of protection"².
- "A limit to present the maximum level of risk above which no individual can be exposed"².

An approach includes **the risk compared with other risks prevalent in society** when it incorporates:

- Comparisons with risk previously determined to be tolerable.
- Comparisons with similar risk reduction technologies.

An approach includes **degree of voluntariness** when it incorporates:

- "Whether an activity is acceptable in terms of the risk involved for the total population"³.
- Undermining the possibility of voluntary risk taking.

An approach includes **the risk as compared with natural background** when it incorporates:

- A comparison that suggests the increment to risk afforded by an activity.
- Analyses of the increase in risk.

An approach includes **existing solutions** when it incorporates:

- The reviewing of existing solutions.
- The results of other studies about risk evaluation.

An approach includes **the risk of available substitutes** when it incorporates:

- The checking of the actions designed to reduce risks for possible bigger risks.
- The consideration that risk is likely to accrue from increased use of substitutes.

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566

Figure 4. Checklist

567 Figure 4 is a check list as guidance on how to decide if an approach includes an element. If one
 568 of the two boxes is ticked, than automatically it qualifies.

569 5.5.1plexity

570 First of all, the complexity of the social context in Solotvyno. As we already mentioned, the case
 571 of Solotvyno is unique, and therefore needs a specific risk evaluation approach. It is a place with a
 572 deep-rooted culture, many different nationalities and beliefs [36]. Apart from the Ukrainians,

573 Solotvyno is the home for a lot of other nations such as Hungarians, Romanians, Roma, Slovaks,
574 Germans, Russians and more of the former Union of Soviet Socialist Republics [36]. As a result, there
575 are a lot of different cultures, norms and values. In finding a suitable risk evaluation approach, all
576 these different groups must feel heard.

577 The risk in Solotvyno is caused by the mining of salt, which at the time brought benefits for some
578 of the residents and risk for others [32]. This makes this case more unique and more complex. Not all
579 residents wanted the same thing, and even now, not everyone agrees with each other about what
580 should happen with the salt domes in the future [37, 38].

581 Because it is a unique and complex situation, a specific approach had that met Solotvyno's
582 requirements had to be found. In the analytical framework, we have described what the necessities
583 are for a suitable risk evaluation approach for Solotvyno. This information allowed us to pick the best
584 approach for this specific case.

585 *5.5.2 Separating risk evaluation approaches from risk appraisal approaches*

586 While looking for risk evaluation approaches, we have often come across risk appraisal
587 approaches. The search terms we used are only about evaluation, and they do not mention risk
588 appraisal. We selected all the articles with approaches that were labeled risk evaluation approaches
589 and ended up with quite a few articles. However, after thoroughly studying the articles, we found
590 out that most of the approaches we found with these terms were about risk appraisal.

591 The term risk evaluation is often used incorrectly to indicate risk appraisal methods. The goal of
592 risk evaluation is to determine the tolerability and acceptability of a given risk. Risk appraisal entails
593 assessing the identification and estimation of hazards.

594 The use of wrong terms made searching for risk evaluation methods more complex. More than
595 once we incorporated a risk appraisal method in our research by mistake, which we eliminated when
596 we concluded that it was not a real risk evaluation approach.

597 For well executed research with risk evaluation approaches as the main subject, there must be
598 the certainty that it is actually about risk evaluation and not about risk appraisal. To be sure of this,
599 every approach was checked several times to see if it was about acceptability and tolerability, and
600 not about assessing risk.

601 *5.6 Assumptions and limitations*

602 The four-risk evaluation approaches we picked are criteria-based methods. To decide whether
603 an approach met an element, we read the criteria with their explanations, if there was an explanation.
604 However, none of the articles explained the criteria in great detail. As a result, it was difficult to
605 estimate whether certain elements are included in an approach.

606 It was a limitation to arrive at the best risk evaluation because there is no full information about
607 each approach. Because not every criterion was explained in detail, assumptions had to be made
608 about if an approach did include an element or not. We applied the same assumptions to all
609 approaches so that the assessment would be fair.

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612 *5.7 Future research*

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Future research (always contain supplementary information, it is essential to be able to assess,)

617 **5. Conclusions**

618 **6. Patents**

619 This section is not mandatory but may be added if there are patents resulting from the work
620 reported in this manuscript.

621 **Supplementary Materials:** The following are available online at www.mdpi.com/xxx/s1, Figure S1: title, Table
622 S1: title, Video S1: title.

623 **Author Contributions:** For research articles with several authors, a short paragraph specifying their individual
624 contributions must be provided. The following statements should be used “conceptualization, X.X. and Y.Y.;
625 methodology, X.X.; software, X.X.; validation, X.X., Y.Y. and Z.Z.; formal analysis, X.X.; investigation, X.X.;
626 resources, X.X.; data curation, X.X.; writing—original draft preparation, X.X.; writing—review and editing, X.X.;
627 visualization, X.X.; supervision, X.X.; project administration, X.X.; funding acquisition, Y.Y.”, please turn to the
628 [CRediT taxonomy](#) for the term explanation. Authorship must be limited to those who have contributed
629 substantially to the work reported.

630 **Funding:** Please add: “This research received no external funding” or “This research was funded by NAME OF
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643 manuscript, or in the decision to publish the results”.

644 Appendix A

645 The appendix is an optional section that can contain details and data supplemental to the main
646 text. For example, explanations of experimental details that would disrupt the flow of the main text,
647 but nonetheless remain crucial to understanding and reproducing the research shown; figures of
648 replicates for experiments of which representative data is shown in the main text can be added here
649 if brief, or as Supplementary data. Mathematical proofs of results not central to the paper can be
650 added as an appendix.
651

652 **Appendix B**

653 All appendix sections must be cited in the main text. In the appendixes, Figures, Tables, etc.
 654 should be labelled starting with 'A', e.g., Figure A1, Figure A2, etc.
 655

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